

Towards the design of artificial surrogates for modelling marine growth

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ABSTRACT: The integration of a primary artificial reef structure as a nature-inclusive design innovation into the floating structure of a floating offshore wind turbine changes the system dynamics and loading conditions. Therefore, experimental hydrodynamic analyses, in which the marine growth colonising the artificial reef structure will be modelled using surrogates, are required during the development of such innovation. In this study, the pertinent literature is reviewed to identify ‘best practice’ for the surrogate design and the characteristics of marine growth that need to be considered. In addition to the well-established relative surface roughness, several other characteristics such as shape, texture, and coverage should be considered in the development of surrogates as they significantly influence the flow and hydrodynamic load conditions. As one of the target sites for the development of the nature-inclusive design, the Baltic Sea has been analysed for the species that dominate offshore structures and need to be considered in marine growth modelling.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to its enormous potential, floating offshore wind (FOW) plays an important role in achieving the European Commission’s ambitious goal of net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 (European Commission 2019). In addition, recent geopolitical events such as the Russia-Ukrainian war have highlighted the importance of renewable energy sources and their impact on energy security and pricing. However, the associated exploitation of the marine environment poses a challenge to conserving and protecting biodiversity (habitats and species) in the European seas. To address this paradox, the INF⁴INiTY project (Windt et al. (2024)) aims to develop nature-inclusive design (NID) innovations for sub-sea components of a tension-leg platform type FOW turbine (see Figure 1). As NIDs are generally species-specific, three case studies for different target areas (Scottish Sea, Baltic Sea, and Adriatic Sea) are considered in the INF⁴INiTY project, for which specific NID innovations will be developed to suit the ecosystem and target species in that area.

One major NID innovation will be a primary artificial reef structure (ARS) integrated into the floating structure, which will serve as a substrate for sessile organisms and provide habitats for fish and other marine life. As a result, significant changes in system dynamics and loading conditions are expected due to increases in member diameter and displaced water volume, drag coefficients, and mass and structural weight (Sarpkaya 1990). Therefore, extensive hydrodynamic analysis, including physical experiments using surrogates to represent marine growth, is required to study the impact of the ARS. Assumptions for layer thickness and density of marine growth as a function of latitude and water depth are given in standards (e.g. NORSOK 2017). However, marine growth is subject to large spatial and temporal variations, and the composition of marine growth is complex, comprising different species with different morphological and mechanical properties. Therefore, analysis of the potential colonisation communities on an ARS integrated into a FOW turbine at the three target sites is essential for realistic modelling of the ARS.

Figure 1: Rendering of GICON[®]'s TLP-type FOW turbine concept (courtesy of GICON[®])

This paper aims to concatenate the basis for the development of the surrogate models, in terms of provisions, conditions, and methods. To this end, the published studies that have used surrogates to model marine growth are first reviewed. The different approaches and results are discussed, which forms the basis for a compilation of relevant marine growth characteristics that should be considered in the development of a surrogate model. Gaps in knowledge are also identified and discussed. Following the literature review, a general methodological approach for the development of surrogate models is then proposed. Finally, the target site analysis is carried out by way of an example for the Baltic Sea. This includes the description of the environmental conditions, the delimitation of the study area based on potential areas of application for FOW and the analysis of the colonisation communities.

2 MARINE GROWTH SURROGATE MODELLING

2.1 Literature review

Numerous studies, both experimental and numerical, have been carried out in the past to gain a better understanding of the fluid-structure interaction of marine growth-covered cylindrical structures. Among the experimental studies, some researchers have used real marine growth, either by immersing the test cylinder in a marine environment for some time (Nath

1984) or by attaching naturally grown marine growth (Theophanatos 1988). However, the use of real marine growth presents a number of difficulties, such as the limited lifespan of the species in the laboratory environment, lack of reproducibility, or scaling limitations. Modelling marine growth using artificial surrogates is therefore the most common approach.

In general, marine growth can be considered as a surface roughness. The degree of roughness is usually described by the relative surface roughness ε . Various definitions of this parameter can be found in the literature (Achenbach & Heinecke 1981, Jusoh & Wolfram 1996, among others), commonly the relative surface roughness is expressed by $\varepsilon = k/D_e$, where k is the roughness height and D_e is the effective diameter of the cylinder (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Definition of the roughness height k , mean growth thickness t , clean cylinder diameter D , and effective diameter D_e (adapted from American Petroleum Institute (2010))

The influence of surface roughness on the flow characteristics around cylindrical structures has been the subject of research for decades due to its practical importance for offshore structures (Achenbach 1971, Güven et al. 1980, Ribeiro 1991, Okajima et al. 1999, van Hinsberg 2015, among others). In these studies, surface roughness was usually created by applying sandpaper, sand, gravel, or glass particles to the test cylinder. While these studies have contributed to the understanding of the basic flow mechanisms, the artificial materials used are not representative of the shape and texture of real marine growth. Marine growth generally is a complex composition of both hard and soft species. In the following, the focus is put on studies that have used more advanced approaches to model marine growth.

The studies by Theophanatos (1988) and Theophanatos & Wolfram (1989) are among the first to comprehensively investigate the effects of marine growth. In these studies, both real marine growth and artificial surrogates were used and different roughness types (hard and soft), different roughness heights, and partial coverage were considered. The surrogates were made of graded sand, gravel, and polystyrene panels in the shape of equilateral pyramids. The result of these studies show that characterisation by the relative roughness parameter alone is not sufficient from a hydrodynamic point of view. Instead, the type of marine growth (hard/soft), its shape, the surface coverage ratio, and distribution should be taken into account.

Baarholm & Skaugset (2008) investigated how marine growth influences the effectiveness of helical

strakes in mitigating vortex-induced vibrations (VIV). Both hard and soft marine growth with different roughness heights relative to the strakes and different coverage ratios were considered. Pebbles glued to the test riser were used to represent barnacles. While the authors reported good experience with the chosen approach for the hard marine growth surrogates, the selection of a suitable surrogate for the soft marine growth, which was to represent marine grass, proved more challenging. After testing various materials for their behaviour and durability in water, different types of fabric/carpet with defined yarn lengths and densities were selected. The authors acknowledge that the selection was based on more qualitative considerations. Ultimately, the results showed clear differences in how different marine growth types affected VIV. While the effect of hard marine growth increased with increasing height, a small height of soft marine growth already caused a significant response.

Henry et al. (2016) investigated the effects of different types of marine growth (hard and soft) on the wake structure behind a cylindrical structure. They followed the approach of modelling hard marine growth by equivalent sand roughness and used artificial fur as a surrogate for soft marine growth. Their results confirm the findings of Theophanatos & Wolfram (1989) and Baarholm & Skaugset (2008) that the effect of the different types is dissimilar.

Zeinoddini et al. (2016) and Zeinoddini et al. (2017) conducted studies on the VIV of cylinders covered with hard marine growth. They modelled colonisation of barnacles with CNC-machined pyramidal and 3D-printed hemispherical bump shapes and considered different coverage ratios. The shape of the roughness appeared to play a minor role compared to the coverage ratio. Low coverage ratios (30 and 50 %) led to VIV suppression of around 43 %. In contrast, high coverage (80 %) provided significantly lower suppression of around 32 %.

Jadidi et al. (2018) also modelled barnacles but with truncated cones. In addition to a regular arrangement pattern, the authors used a Poisson clustering process to generate an aggregated spatial distribution that realistically represents the neither regular nor random distribution of barnacle colonies. Three different coverage ratios were considered. The modified shape resulted in minor changes to the maximum oscillation amplitude and force coefficients, but significantly impacted other VIV dynamics like the onset of oscillations and the lock-in range. The aggregated spatial distribution led to an 11 % increase in maximum oscillation amplitude and a 21 % increase in maximum lift force coefficient at a moderate coverage ratio (66 %). Jadidi & Zeinoddini (2020) extended the approach by incorporating a height distribution model to account for the varying shell heights in a barnacle colony. The results show that non-uniformity in height also affects VIV dynamics. The effect increases with an increasing coverage ratio. With full

coverage, the maximum oscillation amplitude is reduced by approximately 26 % for a uniform height distribution and by around 34 % for a non-uniform height distribution compared to the smooth cylinder.

Landmann et al. (2021, 2021) and Gieschen et al. (2021) conducted experiments with live blue mussel dropper lines to evaluate their hydrodynamic coefficients and developed surrogates with comparable hydrodynamic behaviour. Based on the assumption that the surface geometry significantly influences the hydrodynamic behaviour, the authors aimed at a precise surface description of the live blue mussels. To that end, the Abbott-Firestone Curve (AFC) surface descriptor (Abbott & Firestone 1933) was used to compare the surface geometries of the live mussels with the developed surrogates. The AFC describes the surface geometry through the cumulative material distribution as a function of the surface heights. The reference AFC of the live mussels was created based on a 3D point cloud obtained by laser scanning. Three surrogate types with similar surface geometry characteristics were developed. The first concept was based on the statistical mean data (volume, weight, length, and width) of the live mussels. This data was used to design a uniform mussel, which was randomly arranged around a cylinder by each mussel's rotation. The resulting AFC deviated the most from the reference AFC. For the second concept, a meshed section of the 3D point cloud was used whose AFC best matched the reference AFC. The last surrogate design represented an exact reproduction of the reference AFC through a simpler geometry. The tests with the live mussels and the three surrogate designs under steady and oscillatory flow showed that the performance of the surrogates deviated under steady flow, but generally showed a good fit under oscillatory flow. Overall, the first surrogate concept showed the best fit.

Marty et al. (2021, 2021b) investigated the hydrodynamic influence of marine growth roughness on slender cylinders, e.g., representative of legs and struts of jacket structures. With regard to possible simplifications for future studies, the researchers were interested in the question of what influence a realistic representation of the hard marine growth in terms of geometry and density affects the load estimation. To this end, quantitative data obtained from underwater images of an anchoring chain fully covered by adult mussels were used for the development of surrogates. By analysing the data it was found that the organization is not entirely random and that the orientation of the individual mussels can be approximated by eight angular values. To evaluate whether the realistic representation of the mussels in terms of size affects the loading, two different mussel sizes were considered. Through different combinations of these two and the smooth cylinder, a total of seven surrogate designs were developed representing different growth stages. The surrogates were manufactured through 3D printing. The results show that the two

roughness heights lead to significantly different forces on the cylinders. The different roughness configurations showed smaller differences.

Motivated by the findings of previous studies, Marty et al. (2022) investigated two types of large hard marine growth. The first type was mussel colonisation represented by the surrogates as presented in Marty et al. (2021, 2021b). The second type was coral colonisation as found in tropical waters modelled by large spheres. Two configurations were developed to consider the polyps that can be retracted and extended by the corals. One in which the corals with retracted polyps are represented by spheres with a smooth surface. And a second one, in which the extended polyps are represented by superimposed small-scale roughness in the form of small craters evenly distributed on the spheres. The results confirm the finding of previous studies that the height and shape of roughness significantly influence the hydrodynamic behaviour. The larger coral roughness led to an increase in the drag coefficient of around 50% compared to the smaller roughness (mussels). Furthermore, the differences between the two large roughness configurations (with/without superimposed micro-roughness) also showed to influence on the hydrodynamic coefficients. The surrogate with superimposed micro-roughness showed a drag coefficient around 15% higher than the smooth surface.

Recently, two studies have used surrogates to model the soft marine hydroid species *Ectopleura larynx* (Rashki et al. 2022, Aalami Harandi et al. 2024). While Rashki et al. (2022) investigated the energy harvesting performance of one-degree-of-freedom oscillators colonised by this species, Aalami Harandi et al. (2024) studied its effect on VIV dynamics. Both took a similar approach to material selection. This was based on fibre dimensions and movement in water. Rashki et al. (2022) selected synthetic long pile plush fabrics and Aalami Harandi et al. (2024) used polished fabrics. In addition, three coverage ratios were considered in both studies, with Aalami Harandi et al. (2024) choosing these in line with the study by Jadidi et al. (2018) to allow comparison between hard and soft marine growth. The results of Rashki et al. (2022) showed that soft marine growth significantly reduces the energy harvesting efficiency. Variation of the coverage ratio was found to have a relatively small effect. The results of Aalami Harandi et al. (2024) showed that the presence of marine growth has a significant mitigating effect on VIV dynamics. While the increase from soft to medium coverage showed little relative change, the increase from medium to full coverage showed a significant decrease in hydrodynamic loading. Through comparison with the results of Jadidi et al. (2018), the author concluded that for systems with similar physical and mechanical properties, soft marine growth at higher coverage ratios would be expected to result in at least 10% lower VIV dynamics compared to hard marine growth.

2.2 Relevant characteristics

In the literature reviewed, various characteristics of marine growth have been incorporated into the development of surrogates. For future development of surrogates, it would be desirable to quantify the importance of each characteristic. However, this is a difficult task as the results of the reviewed studies showed complex interactions between parameters and different parameters have received different attention. The relevant characteristics identified are therefore only listed here (Table 1) and their significance is briefly discussed in qualitative terms.

Table 1: Characteristics of marine growth relevant to the design of surrogate and the associated studies

Characteristics	Studies
Relative surface roughness	Theophanatos (1988) Theophanatos and Wolfram (1989) Marty et al. (2021, 2021b, 2022)
Shape	Landmann et al. (2019, 2021) Gieschen et al. (2021) Zeinoddini et al. (2016, 2017) Jadidi et al. (2018) Marty et al. (2021, 2021b, 2022)
Texture (hard/soft)	Theophanatos and Wolfram (1989) Baarholm and Skaugset (2008) Henry et al. (2016) Jadidi et al. (2018) Aalami Harandi et al. (2024)
Coverage ratio	Theophanatos (1988) Theophanatos and Wolfram (1989) Baarholm and Skaugset (2008) Zeinoddini et al. (2016, 2017) Jadidi et al. (2018) Jadidi and Zeinoddini (2020) Rashki et al. (2022) Aalami Harandi et al. (2024)
Spatial arrangement	Jadidi et al. (2018)
Height distribution	Jadidi and Zeinoddini (2020)
Superimposition	Marty et al. (2022)

The results of the early studies of Theophanatos (1988) and Theophanatos & Wolfram (1989) have already shown that a single-parameter characterisation with the relative surface roughness $\varepsilon = k/D_e$ is not sufficient and that more parameters govern the effects of marine growth. However, the importance of ε has been highlighted again, particularly by the studies of Marty et al. (2021, 2021b, 2022). It can be assumed that the surface protrusion field, which is described by the relative roughness, is the most influencing parameter of hard marine growth.

The shape of the marine growth also plays an important role as highlighted by several recent studies. In the studies by Landmann et al. (2019, 2021) and Gieschen et al. (2021) of three different surrogate types, the one with the most realistic shape representation performed best. Comparison of Marty et al. (2021)'s results with studies that considered similar roughness but less realistic shape modelling revealed significant differences. With regard to VIV, however,

Jadidi et al. (2018) and Zeinoddini et al. (2017) both reported that the shape had only a minor effect on the maximum oscillation amplitude and the force coefficients. Yet, other VIV characteristics, such as the onset of oscillation or the lock-in range, changed significantly when the shape was changed.

Next, it can be concluded that the influence of different types of marine growth (hard and soft) is dissimilar. This was demonstrated in particular by Baarholm & Skaugset (2008) and by comparison of the results of the two studies Jadidi et al. (2018) and Aalami Harandi et al. (2024).

The coverage ratio has been incorporated in many studies and has generally been shown to have a significant influence on hydrodynamics. The complexity was particularly highlighted by Aalami Harandi et al. (2024), who observed a non-linear response of VIV dynamics with increasing coverage of soft marine growth, and by Jadidi et al. (2018) and Jadidi & Zeinoddini (2020), who showed that the coverage ratio influences the effects of other characteristics.

Most of the studies reviewed assumed a uniform spatial arrangement of marine growth. However, some species, such as barnacles, show aggregation patterns that are neither regular nor random. Taking this into account, Jadidi et al. (2018) found that spatial arrangement has a significant influence.

Also generally assumed to be uniform is the height of the individual roughness elements. However, again, this does not correspond to reality. Jadidi & Zeinoddini (2020) included non-uniform height distribution in investigations on the performance of VIV converters. The results showed that the uneven height distribution additionally reduces the performance compared to the uniform height distribution, which was particularly evident with large coverage ratios.

Finally, the results from Marty et al. (2022) showed that small-scale roughness superimposed on macro-roughness affects the hydrodynamic behaviour. It can therefore be concluded that not only the largest roughness elements but also the superimposition of smaller roughness elements should be taken into account.

2.3 Limitations and knowledge gaps

Despite the numerous findings of previous studies on the modelling of marine growth, some questions remain unanswered. Most of the reviewed studies have assumed homogeneous single-species colonisation. In fact, however, marine growth is generally complex and diverse. The cohabitation of hard and soft vegetation and the resulting influence on hydrodynamics remains largely unexplored. This may be due to the difficulty of systematically studying real marine growth under controlled laboratory conditions. Prior to establishing general rules for the development of surrogate surfaces of marine growth, it will be paramount to understand the complex flow-structure-interaction between marine flow fields and species-

rich marine growth in marine environments. Furthermore, the choice of surrogate material for modelling soft marine growth has been based more on qualitative considerations, such as the movement of the fibres in the water. The exact shape and mechanical properties such as bending stiffness were not considered so far. A major concern with experiments is scale effects. Comparative data with real marine growth is scarce, making it difficult to assess these effects. Finally, the appropriate ranges of non-dimensional numbers, such as the Reynolds, Cauchy, or Keulegan-Carpenter numbers have not been well-defined, and this will inevitably hamper a comprehensive research stride to elucidate the complex flow processes.

3 METHODOLOGY FOR SURROGATE DEVELOPMENT

The proposed methodology for the development of surrogates for use in hydrodynamic testing is shown in Figure 3. The first step is to describe the marine environmental parameters of the target site that influence marine growth. These include aquatic parameters, such as salinity and oxygen content, as well as hydrodynamic parameters, such as wave and current conditions. Next, the likely colonisation of the structure at the target site is described. To this end, observations of colonisation on existing offshore structures such as monopiles, bridge piers, oil platforms, or existing artificial reefs will be analysed. As the floating structure and its surface are different from the usual vertical steel structures (cf. Figure 1), it is necessary to consider which additional species could potentially colonise. The identified and expected species are then described in terms of their characteristics relevant to the development of the surrogate, taking into account the environmental parameters described above. Where available data permits, it is desirable to provide information on all the characteristics presented in Table 1. The database with the collected properties forms the basis for the design development of the surrogate. This includes the development of the representation of the individuals (e.g. shape, size, aggregation) as well as the distribution of the species around the structure's surface. Subsequently, suitable materials and manufacturing methods are selected.

Figure 3: Methodology for surrogate development for use in hydrodynamic analysis

4 CASE STUDY BALTIC SEA

4.1 *The Baltic Sea*

The Baltic Sea in Northern Europe is one of the world's largest brackish seas. The Baltic Sea is challenging for many species to colonise due to the strong influence of both marine and freshwater environments. Presently, the waterbody is brackish with a gradient in surface salinity from around 14 PSU in the Danish strait down to 3-4 PSU in the most northern part (Bay of Bothnia), and between 7-9 PSU for the central region (Baltic Proper) (see Figure 4c). For many marine and freshwater organisms, this salinity range encompasses the lower and upper tolerance range, respectively (Remane 1934), and the Baltic Sea's ecosystems are low in species richness (Ojaveer et al. 2010). Large areas of the deep bottom below 50 meters depth (see Figure 4a) are also inhabitable due to oxygen-free or oxygen-poor conditions. These conditions are naturally caused by the restricted inflow of deep water through the Danish strait (Zillén et al. 2008) and exacerbated by pollution of inorganic nutrients (Kahru et al. 2020). In addition, overfishing, toxic pollution, invasive species, and climate change are adding stress to local populations (Reusch et al. 2018). Certain notable groups of marine species including tunicates, echinoderms, most sponges, anemones, and oysters (Degraer et al. 2020) cannot tolerate the low salinity in the Baltic Proper. Yet, a few key species are able to tolerate these challenging conditions and form the foundation of the ecosystems. Sessile organisms like blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis/trossulus*), bay barnacles (*Balanus improvises*), bladder wrack (*Fucus vesiculosus*), and eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) have successfully colonised the Baltic Sea through morphological and reproductive adaptations (Johannesson et al. 2020, Snoeijs-Leijonmalm et al. 2017).

4.2 *Study area*

Although the FOW technology is not to be developed for a single location within the Baltic Sea target site, the study area can be narrowed down based on considerations of water depth and wind resources. The TLP-type FOW turbines are designed for water depths, h , around $50 \text{ m} \leq h \leq 100 \text{ m}$. Based on the depth map in combination with the wind resources shown (see Figures 4a and 4b), it can be seen that a large part of the Baltic Sea Proper (area framed in red) is particularly suitable as an application area for FOW.

4.3 *Colonisation communities*

The distribution of sessile marine species is mainly controlled by the availability of suitable habitats to colonise. Factors influencing if a species successfully colonises an available area are complex and include

the availability of food for suspension feeders, availability of light for photosynthesising algae, exposure to predation, tolerance to desiccation, competition for space with other species, and the ability to tolerate exposure to mechanical stress from waves and currents. For artificial structures the depth, material, shape, and orientation (horizontal or vertical) will also affect which organisms will colonise specific components (Andersson et al. 2009, Degraer et al. 2020, Qvarfordt 2006). The majority of studies describing the colonisation of OWF to date have been conducted on monopile structures in shallower seas between 5 m to 40 m depth (Degraer et al. 2020, Langhamer 2012).

Since the floating structure of the FOW turbine in the present study will extend down to a similar depth $\mathcal{O}(10 \text{ m})$ it is reasonable to assume that the vertical zonation in colonising species will be similar to monopile structures in the Baltic Proper (Andersson & Öhman 2010, Wilhelmsson & Malm 2008). However, when FOW turbines are located offshore at a long distance from the source population, the colonisation by larvae and macroalgae polyps may restrict species from colonising suitable habitats. A higher degree of wave exposure may also affect the densities and morphology of sessile organisms, especially macroalgae, compared to populations in more sheltered regions close to the coast. On the other hand, the FOW structure will be more complex than vertical monopiles (cf. Figure 1) and outfitted with NID structures that promote colonisation of sessile organisms (Guerin et al. 2007, Hermans et al. , Sella et al. 2022). Although FOW structures have some unique features, the colonisation process can be assumed to largely follow that of monopile structures but potentially be colonised by a more diverse set of sessile species. Table 2 lists the expected colonisation of the FOW structure. Densities and depth intervals have been predicted based on observations of colonisation of monopile foundations and bridge pillars.

The Monopiles and other artificial structures in the Baltic Proper are dominated by blue mussels, which constitute up to 80 % of the total sessile biomass (Andersson & Öhman 2010, Wilhelmsson & Malm 2008, Qvarfordt et al. 2006, Sokołowski et al. 2017). In addition, bay barnacles are expected to be one of the dominant colonizing species (Andersson & Öhman 2010, Wilhelmsson & Malm 2008, Krone et al. 2013). Algal growth on monopile structures is generally restricted to the photic zone above $\sim 20 \text{ m}$ depth and confined to small filamentous species like *Cladophora* spp., *Ceramium tenuicorne*, *Vertebrata fucoides*, and *Rhodochorton purpureum* (Andersson & Öhman 2010, Wilhelmsson & Malm 2008) with different species occupying different depth niches from the splash zone down to twelve meters depth (see Table 2). Although larger macroalgae, such as bladder wrack, serrated wrack (*Fucus serratus*), and black carageen (*Furcellaria lumbricalis*), are generally not observed on vertical artificial structures in

Figure 4: Baltic Sea conditions, (a) mean depth (HELCOM 2024), (b) wind resources (NEWA 2024), (c) salinity (CMEMS 2018)

Table 2: Compiled information on sessile organisms expected to colonise FOW structures in the Baltic Sea

Common name	Scientific name	Peak bio-mass period	Size [cm]	Density [ind. m ⁻²]	Depth [m]	Surface	Recruitment period
Blue mussel	<i>Mytilus edulis/trossulus</i>	>2 years	4-8	<12000 ^{1,2,3,5}	3-30	All	May-Novembe ⁴
Bay barnacles	<i>Balanus improvisus</i>	< 1-2 years	1-3	<11000 ^{1,2,3}	0-6	All	June-November ⁴
Filamentous green algae	<i>Cladophora</i> spp.	early summer	1-5	30 ^{1,3}	0-3	Mainly concrete	Year around (mainly spring) ⁶
Filamentous red algae	<i>Vertebrata fucoides</i> (<i>Polysiphonia fucoides</i>)	>2 years	5-15	100 ^{1,2,3}	3-12	Mainly concrete	October-January ⁶
Filamentous brown algae	<i>Pilayella</i> spp./ <i>Ectocarpus</i> spp.	Summer/fall	1-3	120 ³	1-6	Mainly concrete	December-January ⁶
Bladder wrack	<i>Fucus vesiculosus</i>	Summer/fall	10-30	20 ^{8**}	3-6*	Horizontal and sheltered	May-June ⁶
Serrated wrack	<i>Fucus serratus</i>	Summer/fall	30-60	30 ^{8**}	3-10*	Horizontal and sheltered	May-June ⁶
Black carageen	<i>Furcellaria lumbricalis</i>	Summer/fall	5-10	50 ^{7**}	3-12*	Horizontal and sheltered	Year around (mainly winter) ⁹
Filamentous brown algae	<i>Battersia arctica</i>	Summer/fall	2-8	300 ^{7**}	3-22*	Deepest part of structure	N/A

*assuming exclusion from wave exposed upper region and lower depth range based on inventory data

**no observation data, estimated based on natural occurrences of single species

¹Andersson and Öhman (2010), ²Wilhelmsson and Malm (2008), ³Qvarfordt et al. (2006), ⁴Sokołowski et al. (2017), ⁵Kautsky and Kautsky (2000), ⁶Qvarfordt (2006), ⁷Naturvårdsverket (2010), ⁸Meichssner et al. (2021), ⁹Kostamo and Mäkinen (2006)

the Baltic Proper, they do occur on offshore banks (Naturvårdsverket 2010) and could potentially colonize horizontal or sheltered parts of the FOW structure at depths between 3 m to 12 m. Colonisation of larger macroalgae could also be aided or encouraged through NIDs (Layton et al. 2019, Meichssner et al. 2021, Qvarfordt 2006). The filamentous brown algae (*Battersia arctica*) form dense mats on reefs in the Baltic Proper at depths down to 22 m (Naturvårdsverket 2010, Snoeijs-Leijonmalm et al. 2017); however, since previous studies on artificial structures in the Baltic Sea are confined to the upper 10 m, it is not known if this species could colonize the deeper parts of the FOW structure. Due to restricted competition at depth, blue mussels are otherwise expected to be the main colonizer of the FOW structure from 3 m down to the base.

The succession of species is expected to stabilize relatively quickly after deployment, likely within two or three years (Andersson & Öhman 2010). The initial settling community composition may be influenced by the deployment season (Kostamo & Mäkinen 2006, Qvarfordt 2006, Sokołowski et al. 2017); installation in spring or summer likely favours bay barnacles while an installation in fall or winter could lead

to more filamentous algae like *Vertebrata fucoides*.

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper concerns the design of surrogates for marine growth for the development of a NID innovation for FOW technology. To identify ‘best practice’ in surrogate modelling and the characteristics of marine growth to be considered, the pertinent literature was reviewed, with a focus on studies using advanced marine growth surrogate modelling. These studies show that the effects of marine growth have recently moved into the focus of research, and many studies have used surrogates to model marine growth in experimental investigations. Furthermore, the review shows that (i) the relative surface roughness, (ii) shape, (iii) texture, (iv) coverage ratio, (v) aggregation pattern, (vi) height distribution, and (vii) superimposed roughness influence the hydrodynamic effects. With this information, future studies can develop advanced modelling approaches with reduced model effects. However, the influence of some assumptions and simplifications remains unexplored. This includes the reduction of complex and diverse colonisation to single-species colonisation, as well as surrogate design and

material selection for soft marine growth based on more qualitative considerations.

In addition, the expected colonisation of the FOW turbine with ARS was described for the target site in the Baltic Sea, based on published observations of existing structures, and the characteristics of the species were described. This data forms the basis for the design of the surrogates, which is part of future work.

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